

Regional geophysics of the Caribbean and northern South America: Implications for tectonics

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Additional Supporting Information (Files uploaded separately and in repository)

Captions for Dataset S1, S2 and S3

Introduction

This Supporting Information includes: Data Set S1 consisting of the measured point values of crustal thickness; Date Set S2, a list of the references from which the seismic data was taken; Date Set S3, a list of the references from which the plate boundaries presented on the Figures were extracted; Text S1 that describes the processing steps used to make the crustal thickness map and Figure S1 that shows this map with the crustal thickness values obtained from the seismic velocity models. Additionally, this Supporting Information includes Text S2 and Figure S2 with a comparison of the US Geological Survey (USGS) and International Seismological Commission (ISC) catalogs and some cross-sections to illustrate this comparison; Figure S3 with the data density for the EMAG2v3; Figure S4 with the tests for the residual gravity map and finally the Table S1 with the calculations for the thermal parameters.

Data Set S1. Text file with seven (7) columns. The first column is the record number given to the datapoint in the original database of Mooney (2015). Columns 2 and 3 are the latitude and longitude, respectively. The fourth column is the value of the crustal thickness including the sediments. Column 5 is the elevation at the datapoint (if negative, is the depth of the water). The sixth column indicates whether the seismic profile from which the data was taken was reversed refraction (R), unreversed refraction (U), split refraction survey (S), reflection profile (F), sonobuoy profile (B), seismic tomography (I), earthquake model (E), receiver function model (C), waveform model (W) or other (O). The last column contains the reference in the literature from which the seismic data was taken in a format created by the original authors of the compilation. The full reference can be found in the dataset S2, and the explanation of the format is explained on the caption of it.

Data Set S2. List of the references from which the seismic velocity models were extracted. The format consists of the year of publication, the initial of the last name of the first author and a number differentiating between same number and letter of the first two factors. (e.g., 63B.1 = the year in which the article was published (1963), the initial of the last name of the first author of the article (B), and the number indicating which of the references from "63B" this seismic model was taken (1)).

Data Set S3. List of the references from which the plate boundaries presented on the Figures were extracted.

Text S1. Processing steps to construct the crustal thickness map.

Following Stolk et al. (2013) and Finger et al. (2021), we have constructed a crustal thickness map for the Caribbean and surroundings. This process employs the following steps.

1. Calculation of the adjusted topography (Stolk et al., 2013). In addition to the topography/bathymetry, we used the data on thickness and density of sediments from (Mooney and Kaban, 2010; Tesauro et al., 2014; Finger et al., 2021).
2. Calculation of the residual Moho and interpolation of these values using ordinary kriging.
3. Checking for outliers. For this purpose, the initial residual Moho map is low-pass filtered with a Gauss-type filter with a 135 km boundary wavelength (half amplitude in space domain). Then, all the seismic points that differ by more than 1.35 km (RMS of the residual Moho differences) were removed from the analysis.
4. After restoration of the initial isostatic correction, a pre-final Moho map was calculated.
5. In the areas located far from the existing determinations, the crustal thickness sometimes is out of the acceptable range (6 – 67.5 km). These limits were set on the final model (Fig. 7); however, these areas should not be considered in further analysis.

Figure S1. Comparison between measured crustal thickness values (Data Set S1) and the contoured crustal thickness map presented in Figure 7 of the main text of this paper.

Text S2. Comparison between USGS and ISC Catalogs

We compared the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) and the International Seismological Center (ISC) event catalogs for events $M \geq 4$ from 1 January 2000 to 28 January 2021. For this period, the ISC has almost twice as many events (36,150 events) as the USGS catalogue (19,058 events). With a larger number of events, the ISC catalog permits more reliable interpretations of the geometry and characteristics of the subducting slab. Moreover, a part of the ISC catalog has been manually reviewed, resulting in a higher precision on the location of the slab compared to the events in the USGS catalog. For this reason, we decided to use the ISC catalogue. We selected the time from 1 January 2005 to 30 April 2019, and a magnitude of $M \geq 4$ as it provides enough events to visualize the Benioff zone and because, at the time of the seismicity analysis, all events before 30 April 2019 were already manually reviewed.

Figure S2. Sample comparison of the USGS and ISC catalogs. The more accurate locations and larger number of events in the ISC catalog permits and more reliable interpretation of the geometry of the subducting slabs. Cross-section locations are provided in Figures 8 to 12 of the main text of this paper, which uses the ISC catalog.

Figure S3. Data density for the marine and airborne data for the third version of the Earth Magnetic Anomaly Grid at 2 arc-minute resolution (EMAG2v3). Red rectangle is the study area.

Figure S4. Residual gravity maps for three values of upward continuation of the Bouguer gravity: **a)** 10 km, **b)** 20 km, and **c)** 40 km. The residual gravity map consists of the Bouguer gravity map minus the upper continued Bouguer map. The map obtained with the upward continuation calculated for a height of 40 km was selected as it provides improved resolution of lateral density variations within the Caribbean plate.

	Longitude (°W)	Latitude (°N)	Velocity (km/Ma)	Age (Ma)	Thermal parameter (km)
Cocos	90	10	71.8	15	1077.00
Lesser Antilles	58	16	18.8	80	1504.00

Table S1. Thermal parameter (Kirby et al., 1996) for two subducting oceanic plates. According to Kirby et al. (1996), only slabs with a value greater than 5000 km display deep seismicity (events deeper than 300 km). Age values were taken from Seton et al. (2020) and relative plate motions are from the NNR-MORVEL56 model (REF?) at the coordinates on the Table.